

Synthesis, centrifugal chromatographic separation and fluorescence study of a 2-pyrazoline[†]

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Abstract : The pyrazolines are well known fluorescent brightening agents and are used as chemosensors. The reaction of dibenzalacetone with hydrazine hydrate and acetic acid yielded a mixture of two products (1 and 2), purified by centrifugal chromatographic separation using chromatotron. Compound 1 was characterized as 5-phenyl-3-[(*E*)-2-phenylvinyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole-1-methylcarbaldehyde by ESI-MS, FT-IR, UV, fluorescence spectroscopy, ¹H NMR data and microanalysis. The fluorescence quantum yield has been determined in various solvents and ratio of excited state dipole moment to ground state dipole moment has been determined using solvatochromic method. The compound can be used as efficient fluorescent material in ultraviolet range.

Keywords : Absorption, chromatotron, dibenzalacetone, fluorescence, 2-pyrazoline, quantum yield.

Introduction

Substituted pyrazolines are useful in pharmaceuticals and agrochemical research. Pyrazoline derivatives with a phenyl group at the 5-position possess good film forming properties and also exhibit excellent characteristics of blue photoluminescence and electroluminescence¹. Pyrazolines are also used as optical brighteners and whiteners. Besides, they display various biological activities²⁻⁹. Pyrazolines are well known brightening agents with excellent fluorescent properties. They can absorb light in 300–400 nm range and emit blue fluorescence because of heterocyclic ring^{10,11}. Pyrazolines are widely used in synthetic fibers, fluorescent probe in some elaborated chemosensor in several fields such as recognition of transition metal ions, hole-transport material in the electro photography and electroluminescence fields because they have stronger fluorescence and higher hole-transport efficiency and excellent emitting blueness property¹². The solvatochromic method is based on the shift of absorption and fluorescence maxima in different solvents of varying polarity. Literature survey reveals that under suitable condition, the solvatochromic method yields fairly satisfactory results^{13,14}.

The present paper deals with the synthesis of 5-phenyl-3-[(*E*)-2-phenylvinyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole-1-methylcarbaldehyde (Scheme 1) from the reaction of dibenzalacetone and hydrazine hydrate with acetic acid and purified by standardization of radial separation method by chromatotron. The studies of absorption and fluorescence spectra of this compound have been performed in various solvents. Fluorescence quantum yield in different solvents, solvatochromic shift and ratio of dipole moment of excited to ground state has been determined with a view to investigate the fluorescence based applications.

Results and discussion

ESI-mass spectrum of compound 1 revealed the presence of protonated and pseudo molecular ions at *m/z* 291, 313 and 329 corresponding to (M+H)⁺, (M+Na)⁺, and (M+K)⁺ respectively, indicating the molecular mass to be 290. IR spectrum of 1 showed a strong band for carbonyl group at 1640–1667 cm⁻¹ and band at 1559 cm⁻¹ for C=N. In ¹H NMR spectra ABX pattern was observable, H_A, H_B and H_X appear as doublets at δ 3.01, 3.65 and 5.51 with *J*_{AB} 17.4 Hz, *J*_{AX} 4.5 Hz, *J*_{BX} 13.2 Hz

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Scheme 1. Syntheses of 2-pyrazoline.

characteristic of the 2-pyrazoline nucleus¹⁶. The protons of aromatic ring (integration 10 protons) were observed at δ 7.22–7.51. A pair of doublets was observable at δ 6.73 and 7.14 for the *trans* olefinic protons. On the basis of the spectral data **1** was characterized as 5-phenyl-3-[(*E*)-2-phenylvinyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole-1-methylcarbaldehyde. The compound **1** is isomeric to an already reported¹⁷ molecule with phenyl and styryl positions exchanged.

Absorption and fluorescence characteristics :

Fig. 1 shows the absorption spectrum of **1** in cyclohexane and DMSO, respectively. In cyclohexane the three absorption peaks are clearly distinguishable with peak positions at 313.1, 324.7 and 340.3 nm with the values of molar extinction coefficients 4.5 , 4.92 and 3.26×10^4 , respectively. The peaks correspond to the vibrational structure of first electronically excited state. The high oscillator strength is indicative of highly absorbing molecule which is a characteristic property of dyes. In DMSO the bands are not distinguishable but the absorption spectrum shows resemblance with cyclohexane except for the small red shift (approximate 4 nm). Fig. 2 shows the emission spectrum in cyclohexane and DMSO. In cyclohexane the vibrational structure is quite discernible while in DMSO

Fig. 2. Solvent effect on fluorescence spectra of compound **1** (10^{-5} M) in cyclohexane and DMSO.

the emission is broad banded. The O-O band for emission in cyclohexane lies at 356.21 nm showing a Stokes shift of 1321 cm^{-1} . In cyclohexane the relative fluorescence quantum yield (ϕ_F) is equal to 0.18 while for DMSO $\phi_F = 0.12$. The band position of absorption and emission maxima and quantum yields for other solvents are given in Table 1.

It is observed from the table that the absorption spectrum $\lambda_{1\text{abs}}$, $\lambda_{2\text{abs}}$ and $\lambda_{3\text{abs}}$ are solvent sensitive and the band positions are red shifted with changing solvent polarity. The respective absorption spectrum shows red shift of approximately 4 nm between nonpolar (cyclohexane) to a more polar solvent (DMSO). The fluorescence emis-

sion spectra are characterized by three peaks (λ_{1em} , λ_{2em} and λ_{3em}) while ethanol and DMSO show only two peaks. On going from cyclohexane to DMSO the observed peaks λ_{1em} and λ_{2em} are found red-shifted from 356–366 nm and 372–381 nm, respectively. This bathochromic shift reflects the occurrence of $\pi \rightarrow \pi$ electronic transitions in the 1-acetyl-3-styryl-5-phenyl-2-pyrazoline singlet excited state. Table 1 also gives the measured fluorescence quantum yields in different solvents used under consideration. The observed ϕ_F values found to vary in the range 0.02 to 0.35 for methanol to dioxane, respectively.

Determination of excited to ground stated dipole moment ratio :

The solvato-chromic method is used to determine the excited singlet-state dipole moment of 1-acetyl-3-styryl-5-phenyl-2-pyrazoline by using Bakhshiev's and Kawski-Chamma-Viallet's formula¹⁸⁻²⁰

$$\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f = \frac{2(\mu_e - \mu_g)^2}{hca_0^3} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\nu}_a$ and $\bar{\nu}_f$ indicate the wavenumbers (cm^{-1}) of electronic absorption and fluorescence emission maxima respectively, μ_g and μ_e , the permanent dipole moments in the ground and in the excited singlet states, respectively, a_0 , the Onsager cavity radius, and F_1 is calculated by :

$$F_1 = \left[\frac{D-1}{D+2} - \frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2} \right] \frac{2n^2-1}{2n^2+2} \quad (2)$$

where D indicate the solvent dielectric constant and n , the solvent refractive index. Also,

$$\frac{\bar{\nu}_a + \bar{\nu}_f}{2} = -\frac{2(\mu_e^2 - \mu_g^2)}{hca_0^3} F_2 \quad (3)$$

where the meaning of the symbols is the same as in eqs. (1) and (2), except for F_2 which is defined as follows :

$$F_2 = \frac{2n^2-1}{2(n^2+2)} \left[\frac{D-1}{D+2} - \frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2} \right] + \frac{3(n^4-1)}{2(n^2+2)^2} \quad (4)$$

The Stoke's shifts ($\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$) and $(\bar{\nu}_a + \bar{\nu}_f)/2$ against the solvent polarity functions F_1 and F_2 , respectively were plotted to determine the excited singlet dipole moment and are given in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. The satisfactory results are found of the statistical treatment of Bakhshiev's and Kawski-Chamma-Viallet's correlations. The slope of 177 and intercept of 1513 cm^{-1} with correlation coefficient of 0.91 is found for Bakhshiev's. However, for Kawski-Chamma-Viallet's, the slope, intercept and correlation coefficient are found to be -1177 , 29085 cm^{-1} and 0.94, respectively. The correlation coefficients value was found to be larger than 0.91 showing the good linearity against the majority of solvents. From eqs. (1) and (3), the slopes S_1 and S_2 of the linear graphs corresponding Bakhshiev's and Kawski-Chamma-Viallet correlations are, respectively.

$$S_1 = \frac{2(\mu_e - \mu_g)^2}{hca_0^3} \quad (5)$$

$$S_2 = \frac{2(\mu_e^2 - \mu_g^2)^2}{hca_0^3} \quad (6)$$

Table 1. Electronic absorption, fluorescence and quantum yields of compound **1** in different solvents

Solvent	Absorption maxima			Emission maxima			Quantum yield ϕ_F
	λ_{1abs} , nm ($\epsilon_1 \times 10^4$)	λ_{2abs} , nm ($\epsilon_2 \times 10^4$)	λ_{3abs} , nm ($\epsilon_1 \times 10^4$)	λ_{1em} , nm	λ_{2em} , nm	λ_{3em} , nm	
Cyclohexane	313 (4.5)	325 (4.9)	340 (3.3)	356	372	396	0.18
Carbontetrachloride	316 (4.1)	328 (4.6)	344 (2.8)	363	379	410	0.03
Chloroform	314 (3.6)	326 (3.9)	342 (2.4)	362	376	401	0.04
Ethanol	311 (3.0)	322 (3.2)	337 (1.8)	353	368	–	0.07
Ethyl acetate	313 (5.5)	325 (5.6)	341 (2.2)	360	374	397	0.19
Dioxane	315 (3.5)	327 (3.9)	343 (2.4)	362	377	397	0.35
Methanol	311 (4.9)	320 (5.2)	335 (3.0)	355	370	391	0.02
Acetonitrile	312 (3.1)	323 (3.3)	338 (2.0)	358	373	392	0.05
DMSO	317 (5.1)	329 (5.5)	344 (3.3)	366	381	–	0.12

Fig. 3. Bakhshive correlation between spectral shifts and the F_1 solvent polarity function.

Fig. 4. Kawski-Chamma-Viallet correlation between spectral shifts and the F_2 solvent polarity function.

The ratio of the first excited singlet state and the ground state dipole moments is calculated by using the relation^{21,22} :

$$\frac{\mu_e}{\mu_g} = \left| \frac{S_1 + S_2}{S_1 - S_2} \right| \quad (7)$$

The experimentally obtained ratio of 1.4 shows that the dipole moment of 1-acetyl-3-styryl-5-phenyl-2-pyrazoline is moderately larger in the first excited singlet state than in the ground state. The comparatively higher value of μ_e than μ_g suggests the existence of difference in the electronic charge distribution in the excited singlet state relative to the ground state. This result confirms that an extended π electronic delocalized system is present throughout the organic compound, with important charged resonance structures in the excited singlet state²¹. The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ may increase the magnitude of charges leading to increase in the dipole moment of 5-phenyl-3-[(*E*)-2-phenylvinyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole-1-methylcarbaldehyde in excited state.

Conclusion

2-Pyrazoline, **1**, namely 5-phenyl-3-[(*E*)-2-phenylvinyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole-1-methylcarbaldehyde was synthesized and characterized by spectral and fluorescence studies. The absorption and fluorescence spectra were measured in various solvents. A ratio of ground and excited state dipole moment was found to be 1.4. The quantum yield values in different solvents were found to vary in between 0.02 for methanol to 0.35 for dioxane. Characterization of **2** and fluorescence properties of solid film of synthesized compounds are in progress.

Experimental

All the starting materials and the solvents used in the present study namely, cyclohexane, carbon tetrachloride, methanol, ethanol, 1,4-dioxane, acetonitrile, dimethylsulfoxide, ethylacetate and chloroform were of GR/spectroscopic quality. A mixture of compounds which was separated through radial chromatographic technique (chromatotron) using silica gel-G TLC grade (2 mm thick) and hexane-ethyl acetate in 95 : 5 ratio as adsorbent and mobile phase, respectively, at 1.5 ml/min flow rate. The maximum flow rate of mobile phase depends upon the density and viscosity of solvents. Fifty ml fractions were collected and progress of elution was monitored by TLC using hexane-ethyl acetate as mobile phase. Melting points are recorded in open glass capillary with Metzer apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded with KBr in Perkin-Elmer FT-IR-RX-01 spectrophotometer. The absorption spectra of the 5-phenyl-3-[(*E*)-2-

phenylvinyl]-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazole-1-methylcarbaldehyde were recorded at room temperature (298 K) with the help of Lambda-35 Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The fluorescence spectra were recorded by using spectrofluorimeter (Perkin-Elmer LS-55). ESI-mass spectra were recorded on MICROMASS QUATTRO II triple quadrupole mass spectrometer. The fluorescence quantum yields were determined using quinine sulfate as the standard ($\phi_F = 0.54$ at 25 ± 5 °C). ¹H NMR spectra were obtained in CDCl₃ on Bruker Spectroscopin DPX-300 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard.

Procedure for the synthesis of dibenzalacetone :

Dibenzalacetone was prepared by reported method¹⁵.

Synthesis of 2-pyrazoline :

To a mixture of 5 mmol of dibenzalacetone in 5 ml acetic acid, 10 mmol of hydrazine hydrate in 5 ml ethanol was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h with constant stirring; the resultant solution was cooled and poured in to crushed ice. The crude reaction products were radial chromatographed to afford compounds **1** and **2**. Compound **1** recrystallized from ethyl acetate.

5-Phenyl-3-[(E)-2-phenylvinyl]-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole-1-methylcarbaldehyde (1) :

Yield 40%; m.p. 118–120 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₂O : C, 78.62; H, 6.20; N, 9.65. Found : C, 79.26; H, 6.36; N, 9.92; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1667 (-C=O), 1559 (C-N), 1326 (C=N); MS *m/z* : 291, 313, 329; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, δ /ppm) : 2.37 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.01 (1H, dd, *J* 4.5, 17.4 Hz, H-4 *trans*), 3.65 (1H, dd, *J* 13.0, 17.4 Hz, H-4 *cis*), 5.51 (1H, dd, *J* 4.5, 13.2 Hz, H-5), 6.73 (1H, d, *J* 16.2 Hz, H- α), 7.14 (1H, d, *J* 16.2 Hz, H- β), 7.22–7.51 (H, m, 10 arom.).

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